

Evaluation of antibacterial activity of some Schiff bases

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Manuscript received 29 April 2008, revised 22 July 2009, accepted 7 August 2009

Abstract : From 4-amino phenol, some Schiff bases were synthesized. By IR and NMR spectral data, the structural characterization of these synthesized compounds were done. The antibacterial activity of all these synthesized Schiff bases was studied against *B. cereus-ATCC 11778*, *P. aero-ATCC 27853*, *E. coli-ATCC 25922*, *K. pneu-NCIM 2719* and *S. aureus-ATCC 25923*, by agar ditch method in dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulfoxide. It is observed that antibacterial activity depends on the molecular structure of Schiff base, solvent used and bacterial strain under consideration. Out of two solvents studied, dimethyl formamide is proved to be best and salicylaldehyde as side chain to 4-amino phenol could be used as lead molecule in drug designing i.e. in inhibiting above bacterial strains.

Keywords : Schiff bases, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Day by day, Schiff bases are integrally applied for human welfare. They are known to be important due to their vivid applications such as preparation of dyes, liquid crystals, powerful corrosion inhibitors and biochemical reactions¹. Many Schiff bases have been found to demonstrate wide range of pharmacological activities like antibacterial, antifungal, anti-HIV, antitumor, antiinflammatory, antipyretic etc.²⁻⁶.

Considering the aforesaid, the aim of present work was to synthesize some Schiff bases from 4-amino phenol and to evaluate their antibacterial activity in dimethyl formamide (DMF) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO).

Experimental

The requisite amount of aldehyde was dissolved in 20 ml methanol. 0.1 mole of amine and few drops of glacial acetic acid were added to it and the mixture was refluxed for 10–12 h at 70–80 °C in a water bath⁷. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature, and then poured over crushed ice with constant stirring. The precipitate obtained was filtered and washed with sodium bisulfite solution to remove excess of aldehyde. The product was crystallized from hot methanol and dried.

Antibacterial activity :

The *in vitro* antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds were tested against some clinically important bacteria viz. *B. cereus-ATCC 11778*, *P. aero-ATCC 27853*,

E. coli-ATCC 25922, *K. pneu-NCIM 2719* and *S. aureus-ATCC 25923* by well diffusion method using Mueller Hinton Agar No. 2 as the nutrient medium. The solutions of Schiff bases (10 mg/ml) were prepared in DMF and DMSO. The bacterial strains were activated by inoculating a loop full of test strain in 25 ml of N-broth and the same was incubated for 24 h in an incubator at 37 °C. 0.2 ml of the activated strain was inoculated in Mueller Hinton Agar at 45 °C. It was then poured in the petri plates and allowed to solidify. After solidification of the media, 0.85 cm ditch was made in the plates using a sterile cork borer and these were completely filled with the test solution. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. The experiment was repeated three times simultaneously under same conditions for each compound and the mean value obtained for the three wells was used to calculate the zone of growth inhibition of each sample. The controls were maintained for each bacterial stain and each solvent, where pure solvent was inoculated into the well. The inhibition zone formed by the Schiff bases were subtracted from the control, against the particular bacterial strain determined the antibacterial activities of the Schiff bases.

Results and discussion

The physical constants such as molecular formula, molecular weight, melting points, % yield and R_f values along with the solvent systems of all Schiff bases are given in Table 1.

Note

Table 1. Physical constants of synthesized Schiff bases

Compd code	Molecular formula	Molecular weight (g/mol)	M p. (°C)	Yield (%)	R _f Value
KPV-1	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂	213.24	140	58.7	0.64
KPV-2	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NOCl	231.68	122	62.5	0.68
KPV-3	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂	227.26	165	67.8	0.14
KPV-4	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	242.23	166	60.5	0.61
KPV-5	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	242.23	162	66.7	0.65
KPV-6	C ₁₁ H ₉ NO ₂	187.20	214	54.3	0.62
KPV-7	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NOCl	231.68	210	53.6	0.14
KPV-8	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₃	243.26	182	61.4	0.64

Ethyl acetate : benzene (2.0 : 8.0); Comp. 1, 2, 4 and 5.

Acetone : benzene (1.0 : 9.0); Comp. 3, 7 and 8

Acetone : benzene (0.3 : 9.7); Comp. 6

The spectral data of these compounds are given below :

4-[[4-Methoxyphenyl]imino]methyl}phenol (KPV-1) :
 IR : 3400–3200 (br, s), 1612 (s), 1593 (s), 1377 (as), 1276, 1172, 1045, 829, 617; Mass : 214 (M+1), 196, 154, 136, 120, 107; NMR : δ_H 4.52 (1H, s), 4.91 (1H, s), 8.28 (1H, s), 6.24 (4H, s), 6.60–6.62 (2H, dd), 6.92 (1H, qt), 7.32 (1H, d).

4-[[2-Chlorophenyl]methylene]amino}phenol (KPV-2) :
 IR : 3398 (br, s), 1616 (s), 1504 (s), 1361 (as), 1111, 972, 837, 810; Mass : 232 (M + 1), 196, 167, 154, 136, 120, 107; NMR : δ_H 4.30 (1H, s), 8.1 (1H, s), 6.20 (4H, s), 6.30–6.42 (2H, dd), 6.72 (1H, qt), 7.62 (1H, d).

4-[[4-Methoxyphenyl]methylene]amino}phenol (KPV-3) :
 IR : 3300 (br, s), 2927 (s), 1608 (s), 1569 (s), 1365 (as), 1265, 1022 (s), 979; Mass : 228 (M+1), 213, 196, 154, 136, 120, 107; NMR : δ_H 3.95 (1H, s), 7.6 (3H, s), 5.92 (4H, s), 6.18–6.22 (4H, s).

4-[[2-Nitrophenyl]methylene]amino}phenol (KPV-4) :
 IR : 3320 (br, s), 1610 (s), 1508 (as), 1340 (as), 1271, 1242 (s), 1022 (s) 831, 738, 694; Mass : 243 (M+1), 226, 196, 167, 154, 136, 120, 108; NMR : δ_H 4.40 (1H, s), 8.00 (1H, s), 6.12 (4H, s), 6.79–6.96 (4H, mt).

4-[[3-Nitrophenyl]methylene]amino}phenol (KPV-5) :
 IR : 3350 (br, s), 1620 (s), 1273 (as), 1350 (as), 1103, 1350 (s), 1510 (s), 835, 734, 540; Mass : 243 (M+1), 227, 213, 197, 165, 154, 136, 119, 107; NMR : δ_H 4.42 (1H, s), 8.42 (1H, s), 6.56 (4H, s), 6.62 (1H, d), 6.72 (1H, d), 6.92–6.96 (1H, qt), 7.02 (1H, s).

4-[[2-Furylmethylene]amino}phenol (KPV-6) :
 IR : 3240 (br, s), 1607 (s), 1366 (as), 1508, 1454, 1018 (s), 1234, 1164, 829, 736, 540; Mass : 188 (M+1), 165, 154, 136, 120, 115, 107; NMR : δ_H 4.15 (1H, s), 7.50 (1H, s), 6.42 (4H, s), 7.21 (1H, d), 7.10 (1H, s), 6.88 (1H, s).

4-[[4-Chlorophenyl]methylene]amino}phenol (KPV-7) :
 IR : 3210 (br, s), 1620 (s), 1595 (s), 1350 (as), 1504, 1446, 1274, 1163, 1010, 975, 823; Mass : 232 (M+1), 165, 154, 149, 136, 120, 115, 107; NMR : δ_H 3.92 (1H, s), 8.05 (1H, s), 6.42 (4H, s), 6.72 (4H, s).

4-[[4-Hydroxyphenyl]imino]methyl}-2-methoxyphenol (KPV-8) :
 IR : 3233 (br, s), 2931 (as), 2847 (s), 1596 (s), 1515 (s), 1369 (as), 1512, 1396, 1265, 1163, 1122, 1026, 821; Mass : 244 (M+1), 288, 154, 149, 136, 120, 107; NMR : δ_H 4.20 (1H, s), 8.10 (1H, s), 3.20 (3H, s), 3.82 (1H, s), 6.54 (4H, s), 6.90–6.92 (2H, dd), 7.71 (1H, d).

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity of all the Schiff bases against the above mentioned bacteria are shown in Figs. 1–5. Fig. 1 shows that all the Schiff bases could inhibit *B. cerus*

Fig. 1. Inhibition zones of Schiff bases in DMF and DMSO against *B. cereus*.

Fig. 2. Inhibition zones of Schiff bases in DMF and DMSO against *P. aero.*

Note

Fig. 3. Inhibition zones of Schiff bases in DMF and DMSO against *E. coli*

Fig. 5. Inhibition zones of Schiff bases in DMF and DMSO against *S. aureus*

Fig. 4. Inhibition zones of Schiff bases in DMF and DMSO against *K. pneumoniae*.

vent plays an important role in inhibition. KPV-1 showed maximum inhibition followed by KPV-4. Minimum inhibition is observed by KPV-6. In DMSO also, KPV-1 showed maximum inhibition followed by KPV-6. Minimum inhibition is observed by KPV-3, KPV-7 and KPV-8.

All the Schiff bases have 4-amino phenol as central moiety. The side chains are different. Thus, in different solvents, different side chains show different activity. KPV-1 has salicylaldehyde as side chain which is observed to be most effective in both the solvents. Furfuraldehyde side chain is least effective in DMF than in DMSO.

Fig. 2 shows that against *P. pneumoniae* also, KPV-1 is most effective in both the solvents. However, inhibition is more in DMF than in DMSO. In DMF, KPV-2, KPV-3 and KPV-6 showed minimum inhibition. KPV-4 and KPV-8 are also quite effective in DMF. However, in DMSO, KPV-2, KPV-3 and KPV-8 showed no inhibition against *P. pneumoniae*.

In Fig. 3, inhibition of all the bases is shown against *E. coli* in both the solvents. In DMF, KPV-3 showed maximum inhibition followed by KPV-8. KPV-1 showed minimum inhibition. But, in DMSO, only KPV-1 showed inhibition. Other bases showed no inhibition at all.

both DMF and DMSO solvents. However, inhibition is more in DMF than that in DMSO. This suggests that sol-

Against *K. pneu*, all the bases had significant activity in DMF as shown in Fig. 4. In DMSO, KPV-5 showed maximum activity whereas KPV-6 showed minimum activity.

The inhibition, against *S. aur* for all the bases in DMF and DMSO are shown in Fig. 5. In DMF, inhibition is maximum than in DMSO, KPV-4 and KPV-5 are most effective in both the solvents. In DMSO, KPV-6 and KPV-7 showed no inhibition.

Thus, we conclude that inhibition depends upon solvent, structure and strain. Out of the two solvents studied, DMF proved to be better solvent. 4-Amino phenol moiety is common in all bases but side chains are different which has different effect on different bacterial strains in different solvents. Out of all bases, the base with salicylaldehyde showed maximum inhibition followed by nitro benzaldehyde group.

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